

VuFind

VuFind is an open-source library search engine designed and developed for libraries by libraries. It allows users to search and browse beyond the resources of a traditional Online Public Access Catalog. It has been developed by Villanova University. Version 1.0 was released in July 2010. Since it is open-source it can be modified to fit someone's needs. It is offering keyword searching, suggested resources, personal organisation and also offers versions in several languages.

VuFind is a discovery system which is flexible enough to build search interfaces for all kinds of content beyond the library environment. Its main purpose is to give the user a very user-friendly interface. It provides the user an interface which enables them to search through all their resources in a single-consistent way. It supports a wide range of use cases. It supports building a local index and/or integrating with a variety of existing third party services.

VuFind search index runs on Apache Solr, an open source search engine which offers amazing performance and scalability. It has the ability to be distributed if someone needs to spread the load of the catalog over many servers or in a cloud environment.

VuFind is a software which is modular and highly configurable. It enables the users to search other library resources including local cached journals, digital library items, institutional repository and bibliography. There are around two hundred institutions running live or beta instances of VuFind including the National Library of Finland, the National Library of Ireland, and the Iowa City Public Library as well a dozen of instances run by finc in Germany. It offers a number of features that enhance its usability. Like -

Faceted search results that allow users to narrow items by format, call number, language, author, genre, era, region and more.

Suggested resources and searches.

Browsing capability.

Personal organization and annotation of resources through favorites lists, texting, emailing, tagging, and commenting features.

Persistent URLs.

APA or MLA citations.

Author biographies.

Multi-language capability with translations available in

Brazilian, Portuguese, Chinese, Czech, Dutch, English, French, German, Japanese, Spanish, Bengali and more.

We can conclude that VuFind is maintained by an international community of developers.

Libraries around the world customize and improve VuFind, contributing those improvements back to the project to be shared by all.